

Layout of covered seedlings for tungro production. IRRI.

used in each tungro propagation. About 750 g of TN1 seeds are soaked in water on Mondays. The following day, the soaked seeds are sown in 10-row lots individually covered with improvised cages. Fourteen days after seed soaking,

7,000 to 10,000 adult green leafhoppers are given a 4-day acquisition access time on tungro-diseased plants. Then 1,000 to 1,500 viruliferous insects are introduced into each cage for a 11 inoculation access time of 6 days. After

inoculation, the living insects are recovered from each cage to be used to generate new insect colonies. The seedlings are then pulled for transplanting. The procedures of tungro propagation, from seed soaking to transplanting, take 3 weeks. The present schedule is to prepare the seedbed, soak seeds, and confine insects on diseased plants on Mondays; sow on Tuesdays; harvest on Thursdays; and inoculate seedlings on Fridays.

Use of the propagation method results in the deposit of *N. virescens* eggs on 30,000 seedlings/week (5,000 seedlings/lot); more than 90% of the seedlings are infected. In 65 randomized samplings for the hatchability of eggs laid on seedlings, from 0.01 to 13 nymphs/seedling were found, an average of 7 nymphs/seedling. Transmission tests of nymphs randomly collected from the inoculated seedlings indicated that 64% had acquired the tungro virus and were capable of infecting seedlings. ■

Varietal resistance and possible components of horizontal resistance to blast

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Plants of Tetep, Carreon, IR36, IR442, and Khao-tah-haeng 17 (KTH) were inoculated with *Pyricularia oryzae* isolates 7506 and 2017 at 21 days after seeding. The plants had been grown from seed in pots with high-nitrogen soil under 12-hour day/night temperatures of 29°/21°C. Inoculated plants were placed in a dew chamber at 21°C for 24 hours, then transferred to 25°/11°C day/night temperature conditions. Six days after inoculation the lesions and the spores in each lesion were counted. Three-cm-long leaf pieces with only 1 lesion were excised, washed with distilled water, placed in individual humidity chambers made from petri dishes, and incubated

Table 1. Average number of type 3 (T-3) and type 4 (T-4) blast lesions formed on the upper leaf of 30 plants of 5 rice varieties 6 days after inoculation.

Isolate	Lesions (no.)									
	Tetep		Carreon		IR36		IR442		KTH	
	T-3	T-4	T-3	T-4	T-3	T-4	T-3	T-4	T-3	T-4
2017	0.5	3.9	0.1	0.3	0.1	0.3	0.1	1.5	3.4	16.9
7506	0	0	0	0	0	0.6	0	1.6	0.5	4.0

for 77 hours. Each lesion was vigorously washed in 0.5 ml distilled water and spores were counted with a haemocytometer. Each count was replicated 10 times; 5 lesions/isolate and 5 lesions/variety were examined. The lesions were further incubated for another 72 hours, counted, and then

measured.

When inoculated with either isolate Carreon failed to produce symptoms, indicating vertical resistance to both isolates. Tetep expressed vertical resistance to isolate 7506 but was susceptible to 2017. KTH, IR36, and IR441 were susceptible to both

Table 2. Mean size of lesions on leaves of 4 rice varieties 12, 13, 15, and 24 days after inoculation with two blast isolates.

Days after inoculation	Mean lesion size ^a (mm)					
	Isolate 2017			Isolate 7506		
	Tetep	KTH	IR442	IR36	KTH	IR442
12	4.0 × 2.0	6.4 × 2.0	3.0 × 2.1	7.2 × 2.2	10.4 × 3.3	8.0 × 2.3
13	3.8 × 1.6	6.4 × 2.1	3.4 × 2.0	—	—	—
15	10.0 × 1.4	8.1 × 2.0	3.8 × 2.1	—	16.8 × 2.0	15.2 × 2.0
24	12.6 × 1.7	22.2 × 2.2	20.4 × 2.0	—	19.6 × 2.0	—

^aLength × width.

Table 3. Average number of spores produced by type 4 lesions on 4 rice varieties inoculated with 2 blast isolates and incubated for 36 and 72 hours, from counts at 4 inoculation intervals.

Days after inoculation	Spores (no./m × 1000)											
	Isolate 2017						Isolate 7506					
	Tetep		KTH		IR442		IR36		KTH		IR442	
	36 h	72 h	36 h	72 h	36 h	72 h	36 h	72 h	36 h	72 h	36 h	72 h
6	0.60	0.40	0.02	0.08	0.26	0.28	2.90	1.06	3.28	2.16	1.06	0.54
7	0.28	0.14	0.78	1.02	0.46	0.06	–	–	–	–	–	–
10	0.04	0.10	0.30	0.44	0.28	0.58	–	–	3.48	3.44	1.46	1.28
19	0.24	0.42	0.68	0.36	–	–	–	–	1.22	0.40	0.30	0.81

isolates (Table 1). IR36 had fewer and smaller lesions than IR442 and KTH, indicating that number of lesions and size of lesions may be components of horizontal resistance to rice blast

(Table 1, 2). The variety had no effect on spore production of either isolate of the blast fungus, indicating that sporulation capacity is not a component of horizontal resistance, but is a

reproductive function of the blast fungus. That is further supported by the fact that lesion size did not affect the number of spores per lesion (Table 3).

Reaction of indica and japonica rices to blast in Taiwan

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Five uniform blast nurseries were established yearly from 1974 to 1978 to test rice varieties and selections from various breeding stations for blast reaction in Taiwan. Four were on the western coast (Yilan, Nantou, Chiayi, Pingtung) and one in the east (Taitung). The program was jointly conducted by the Taipei, Taichung, Chiayi, Kaohsiung,

and Taitung stations with the assistance of the Joint Commission on Rural Reconstruction.

Among the 693 entries were 499 japonicas and 194 indicas. Thirty-four percent of the entries showed resistance to leaf blast; 55%, to neck blast. Fifteen and 48% of the japonicas and 75 and 84% of the indicas were resistant to leaf and neck blast, respectively. Japonica varieties generally appear more sensitive to leaf blast; indicas have more overall blast resistance than japonicas under local conditions.

A positive relationship existed between leaf and neck blast reactions (correlation coefficients were 0.77 for

japonicas, 0.64 for indicas, and 0.79 when pooled). All correlations were significant at the 1% level indicating varieties resistant to leaf blast were resistant to neck blast, but a smaller *r* value for indicas may lead to exceptions.

Of 35 varieties being commercially produced (28 japonicas, 7 indicas), only 8 (3 japonicas, 5 indicas) were resistant to both neck and leaf blast. Among the susceptible were two leading varieties, Tainan 5 and Tainung 67; the two were planted on 384,000 ha in 1978 (51% of Taiwan's total planted areas). Chianung 242, until recently one of Taiwan's most popular resistant cultivars, was also susceptible. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Comparison of oxalic acid concentration in rice varieties resistant and susceptible to the brown planthopper

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Resistance to the brown planthopper (BPH) in certain rice varieties is mainly governed by chemicals in the phloem tissues that inhibit sucking. To test oxalic

acid for its potential in inhibiting sucking by BPH, we isolated it from leaf sheath extracts of Mudgo, a resistant variety. We compared the oxalic acid concentration in the following 28 rice varieties, with special reference to differences in their varietal resistance to BPH.

- Susceptible varieties: IR8, IR20, IR22, IR24, TN1
- Resistant varieties with:
Bph 1 gene – IR26, IR32058-78, Mudgo, CO 10, MTU15
Bph 2 gene – IR32, H5, H105,

CR94-13, ASD7

Bph 3 gene – Kuruhondarwala, Gangala, Rathu Heenati

Bph 4 gene – Heenhoranamawee, Babawee, Lekam Samba, Kalukuruwee, Kahata Samba

Unknown gene(s) – PTB21, PTB33, Sudu Hondarwala, Sinna Sivappu, Balamawee

Organic acids were separated from 70% EtOH extracts of fresh leaf sheaths from 40-day-old plants using ion exchange chromatography through Amberlite CG120 and Amberlite